

ATMANIRBHAR BHARAT ABHIYAN: OPPORTUNITIES AND CHALLENGES

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INTRODUCTION

Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan has set the goal of a self-reliant India. It will be accomplished through collaborative, innovative and transformative policy of the government. It is the vision of new India visualised by our Hon'ble Prime Minister Shri. Narendra Modi. He presented the vision to the nation on 12th may 2020, and announced the special economic and comprehensive package of INR 20 lakh crore equivalent to 10% of India's GDP to fight COVID-19 pandemic in India. Government of India announced several bold reforms such as supply chain reforms for agriculture, rational tax, capable human resource and strong financial system. The five pillar of Atmanirbhar Bharat focus on Economy, Infrastructure, System, Vibrant Demography and Demand.

Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan has multiple dimensions encompassing almost every sector of the economy. The future strategy should be based upon the principles of Make in India, Make for the world, education for the 21st century and focus of rural economy rural industries and small Micro and Cottage industries. The Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan is a continuous process of nation building. The Indian economy has to grow fast and move on a high trajectory so as to reach the ambitious 5 trillion US dollars mark by the year 2025.

1. OBJECTIVES OF THE PAPER

1. To study the opportunities of Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan.
2. To study the Challenges of Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan.

2. Research Methodology:

This research is a descriptive study. The necessary information obtained from secondary sources. The secondary resource was collected from the different journals, research papers, articles, books Websites and Govt. Reports.

3. Opportunities of Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan :

1. Atmanirbhar Bharat focus on making India self-reliant and self-sufficient in all aspects, by reducing our dependence on imports from other nations by increasing our capacity to produce most of the items locally. By nourishing local magnification in services and products the Atma Nirbhar Bharat can be made a successful mission.
2. Atma Nirbhar Bharat was mainly in the situation that the things which were imported before the COVID shall be now manufactured in India not only for consumption but also the export.
4. India has demonstrated how it rises up to challenges and uncovers opportunities there in as manifested in the re purposing of various automobiles sector industries to collaborate in the making of life saving ventilators.

5. It shows the seeds for a new course of long term development and serves as the turn on which India can emerge as a hub for manufacturing and investments. In order to achieve this vision, India needs to focus on holistic and sustainable development.
6. Atma Nirbhar Bharat opens the opportunities to rural area people they can start up their business by implementation of the concept like Gobar bank. It will encourage the profession of the cattle-rearing.
7. Atma Nirbhar Bharat promotes a start-up by which students will start to become more inclined towards becoming entrepreneurs. Entrepreneurs may create entirely new markets and industries that become engines of future growth youth unemployment in India.
8. Atma Nirbhar Bharat would integrate India with the world as the concept envisages opportunities to paint green the economic sectors that have the maximum impact on sustainable development
9. The measures announced for the agricultural and allied sectors are particularly transformative. These reforms are steps towards achieving the goal of a self-sustainable rural economy.
10. Atma Nirbhar Bharat Abhiyan has given the importance of MSMEs of the revival of the Indian economy. The campaign has eared INR 3.0 lakh crore collateral free loan facilities for MSMEs under the package. The MSMEs sector is the second largest employment generation sector in India.
11. Public expenditure on health care services will be increased by investing in grass root health institutions and ramping up health and wellness centre across the nation.
12. One of the core features of the Atma Nirbhar Bharat revival package is its focus on increasing the efficacy of coal use. Coal gets INR 500 billion to develop infrastructure. The Government of India has pitched coal gasification enrolment friendly move.

13. Challenges of Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan :

1. Presently 21 century technology, industrial automation, robotics and Artificial Intelligence are changing way of industrial work and making many of the jobs unneeded. India's job market is undergoing these changes and there is need for fresh thinking to address current and emerging challenges.
2. India MSMEs and other companies have often faced unfair competition from foreign companies. MSMEs face problems of marking and liquidity.
3. The rate of registration charges of property is high and our labour laws need to be modernized.
4. The economic packages as required for the country during the Lockdown period enhancing demand throughout the country.
5. The main challenge faced by companies is in supply chains, which increased delay in the services the effect on logistic and also cause the effect on imports. The significant challenges of the supply chain are disruptions in imports.
6. In a lot of industries, India is depended to an extent on countries like china for production and supply chain. The need of the hour is to be self-reliant in these areas.

14. CONCLUSION

Our development indicates the development of our nation, so we should our best for developing ourselves. The Government can only launch a scheme but it is our duty to bring it into action. Atmanirbhar Bharat and have been implemented there is a lots of scope to build India Atmanirbhar. This mission is contributing to job creation, education to continue skill development and digital health mission and one health program to be self-reliant socially. Good opportunity to attain status of Atmanirbhar Bharat in a short of time. Government should invest in developing the education system so that future employees are technology driven and are ready for the industry. Atmanirbhar Bharat Abhiyan campaign is essential to recover the economy from COVID – 19 pandemics, this has some challenges.

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